

Doing AI Differently

Executive Summary

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

Executive summary

Artificial Intelligence is rapidly becoming global infrastructure – shaping decisions in healthcare, education, industry, and everyday life. Yet current AI systems face a fundamental limitation: they are shaped by narrow operational metrics that fail to reflect the diversity, ambiguity, and richness of human experience.

This white paper presents a research vision that positions interpretive depth as essential to building AI systems capable of engaging meaningfully with cultural complexity – while recognising that no technical solution alone can resolve the challenges these systems face in diverse human contexts.

We identify a foundational gap:

AI systems increasingly produce and act upon cultural outputs – language, images, narratives – yet lack frameworks for interpreting the cultural content they generate and encounter.

At the same time, AI is entering domains where success is harder to define: areas without clear ground truth that demand contextual reasoning and interpretive judgement. In such cases, traditional benchmarking breaks down.

These interpretive challenges fall precisely within the expertise of the humanities, arts, and qualitative social sciences – disciplines that specialise in understanding cultural meaning, contextual nuance, and interpretive complexity.

This gap creates measurable deployment failures and ethical risks across diverse contexts, limiting AI's effectiveness and global applicability. We've seen this before: early social media platforms were released with minimal contextual safeguards and benchmarked on simplistic engagement metrics – leading to unanticipated societal harms. AI, now entering even more sensitive domains, must not follow the same path.

But the opportunity is greater than the problem: integrating interpretive capabilities could unlock significant advances in AI's ability to solve complex, real-world challenges while ensuring these technologies amplify rather than erode human potential. This is a critical moment to shape AI's foundations – early design choices will steer its trajectory for years to come.

Three critical challenges

The qualitative turn: AI is no longer limited to structured prediction or optimisation – it now operates in tasks that require contextual judgement, cultural nuance, and interpretive reasoning.

The homogenisation problem: The dominance of a few AI architectures propagates design limitations across countless applications and can entrench social inequalities by reinforcing narrow models of reasoning and representation.

The transformation of human cognition: As we engage with complex, interconnected systems of artificial and human agents, AI is reshaping human thinking and work in ways that risk diminishing rather than enhancing human agency and capabilities.

A new research agenda

Doing AI Differently calls for a fundamental shift in AI development – one that positions the humanities, arts, and qualitative social sciences as integral, rather than supplemental, to technical innovation. This creates *Interpretive AI* – systems designed to handle plurality, ambiguity, and contextual meaning as core capabilities.

The core innovations we envision

Interpretive technologies: AI systems that represent multiple valid perspectives rather than producing monolithic outputs, enabling more nuanced, culturally sensitive reasoning across diverse contexts.

Alternative architectures for AI: Expanding the AI design space beyond current homogeneous approaches through diverse reasoning paradigms grounded in heterogeneous cognitive, cultural, and planetary processes.

Human-AI ensembles: Developing frameworks for sophisticated, collaborative human-AI systems that strengthen our collective intelligence and enhance rather than replace human capabilities in complex decision-making.

Interpretive AI refers to systems designed to engage with ambiguity, context, and plurality as core capabilities. While this work does not aim to substitute for human interpretive agency, it proposes that humanistic methods – including narrative analysis, cultural reasoning, and contextual sensitivity – can inform how AI systems are designed, trained, and evaluated. We recognise this as a high-risk research direction, precisely because many elements of interpretation resist formalisation – and because it challenges prevailing assumptions in both technical and humanistic domains.

This approach builds on and bridges critical gaps between existing fields. While responsible AI addresses ethical deployment, digital humanities leverages computational tools for cultural research, and human-computer Interaction emphasises interface design, this work integrates interpretive reasoning into AI's foundational architecture. Recent breakthroughs like DeepSeek – which achieved competitive performance by integrating humanities scholars directly into technical development teams – demonstrate the measurable value of this approach at scale.

Demonstrating the gap: societal challenges

Sustainability: Scientific consensus on climate change is clear, yet AI-driven pathways for action often ignore the local, cultural, and political specificities that shape real implementation. Interpretive capacity is essential for bridging global models with grounded, diverse realities.

Healthcare: Patients' lived experiences are rich, sensory, and emotional – but often flattened by data-driven systems. Interpretive AI can preserve narrative complexity, supporting better diagnoses, trust, and care outcomes.

Engineering design: Engineering design requires AI systems that can interpret cultural contexts and user meaning, supporting collaborative teams rather than automated optimisation.

Strategic context and momentum

Doing AI Differently has gained significant international traction: 50+ authors and 150+ active researchers across 6 continents, validation by 70+ leading experts, adoption as a UKRI programme theme, and £1M investment by UK's AHRC and Canada's SSHRC for UK–Canada–US collaborations.

This initiative builds on prior work by AI artists, curators, and creative technologists, whose early engagement with AI systems as cultural and interpretive media helped shape the co-creative and epistemic orientation that defines this agenda.

The timing is critical: the systematic erosion of humanities funding is occurring precisely when interpretive expertise becomes technically essential for AI development. The cost of inaction is significant: continued deployment failures, diminished capacity to shape emerging AI economies, and missed opportunities to lead in next-generation AI development.

Roadmap and engagement pathways

Early participants will help shape both the research agenda and the policy frameworks that will define AI's next decade. This white paper provides a concrete roadmap for doing so:

- The research vision and five strategic workstreams to catalyse breakthrough research across disciplines and sectors, outlined in detail in the report.
- A parallel set of policy-facing recommendations, presented in a separate policy note.

Technical foundations will be established by 2026, with demonstrable impact visible by 2030 through AI systems that can effectively operate across diverse cultural contexts.

Call to action

This is more than a report – it is a call to action and a plan for change. We invite researchers, institutions, and funders to join us in this crucial endeavour to unite the humanities, data science, and engineering in shaping the future of AI. This includes deepening collaboration with those whose cultural lives, environments, or rights – and the more-than-human systems they are entangled with – may be shaped by AI, but who are often left out of its design.

By acting now, funders, institutions, governments, industry, and researchers can help shape AI's trajectory – ensuring that this generational technology enhances human capabilities, reflects global diversity, and delivers positive societal outcomes at scale.

A view from the arts

Abstractions like ‘the Machine’ don’t arrive from nowhere – they’re constructed through our existing histories, philosophies, and cultural perspectives. It’s easy to forget that **there’s no such thing as a single artificial intelligence**, because there’s no such thing as a single natural intelligence. There’s meaning in the data – but **it’s not the meaning we are given; it’s the meaning we make.**

Sougwen Chung
(Artist)

A View from Industry

AI needs to be done differently. In its current design as a consumer product, AI has the power to dramatically reduce human agency. Current AI systems take control away from the people who use these tools in important ways: the companies that own these technologies can simply dictate how they function through system prompts and architectural choices. For example, we see the beginnings of AI personalisation designed to enhance corporate profits rather than empower consumers. **In my own response to this problem, I left my role at a major tech company to build AI tools based on different principles – to maximise individual human autonomy.** This white paper identifies the same core problem from another perspective. **Addressing homogenisation and ensuring AI complements, rather than displaces, human capabilities and agency is imperative.** Tackling these urgent issues will require coordinated action from academia, industry, policy, and more. **This paper offers a crucial vision for how a broad coalition can drive this effort forward.**

Edgar A. Duéñez-Guzman
(Co-founder Gibran,
ex-DeepMind)

Full white paper, policy note and methodology available at

www.turing.ac.uk/news/publications/doing-ai-differently

The Doing AI Differently initiative is led by The Alan Turing Institute, University of Edinburgh and the UK's Arts & Humanities Research Council (AHRC-UKRI), in collaboration with international partners.

Publisher: The Alan Turing Institute, London, UK.

Publication Date: 31 July 2025.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.16421465](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16421465)

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Cite as: Hemment, D., Kommers, C., et al. (2025). Doing AI Differently: Executive Summary. London: The Alan Turing Institute

Funded by: Arts & Humanities Research Council and Lloyd's Register Foundation.

Doing AI Differently website: www.doingaidifferently.org

Cover image: Yutong Liu & Kingston School of Art / Better Images of AI / Talking to AI 2.0 / CC-BY 4.0.

Design and typography: Joshua Smythe, Studio Ampersandwich

Brand identity: Steven Scott, twofifths design

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The Alan Turing Institute is the UK's national institute for data science and artificial intelligence. The Institute is named in honour of Alan Turing, whose pioneering work in theoretical and applied mathematics, engineering and computing is considered to have laid the foundations for modern-day data science and artificial intelligence. The Institute's purpose is to make great leaps in data science and AI research to change the world for the better. Its goals are to advance world-class research and apply it to national and global challenges, build skills for the future by contributing to training people across sectors and career stages, and drive an informed public conversation by providing balanced and evidence-based views on data science and AI.